

Several parameters for intrapopulation genetic diversity were estimated for each population using isozyme and RFLP data (Table 2). These parameters showed no correlation between isozyme and RFLP level. The DX and YJ populations, which are completely isolated from cultivated ricefields, showed less polymorphism than the perennial populations from other countries at the isozyme level, but this trend was not found at the RFLP level. The high gene diversity at both the isozyme and DNA levels in the GG population adjacent to cultivated ricefields is probably due to the flow of genes from these neighboring cultivated rices. ■

Genetics

Molecular analysis of introgression in *Oryza sativa*/*O. brachyantha* and *O. sativa*/*O. granulata* derivatives

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The genus *Oryza*, to which cultivated rice belongs, has 20 wild species that provide an important reservoir of useful genes for rice improvement. *O. brachyantha* (2n=24, FF) and *O. granulata* (2n=24), two distantly related species, possess genes for resistance to yellow stem borer, bacterial blight, and brown planthopper. Several backcross progenies of these two species with elite breeding lines of *O. sativa* have been developed and are being analyzed for

possible introgression at the phenotypic and molecular levels.

The objective of our investigation was to determine the nature and magnitude of introgression from *O. brachyantha* and *O. granulata* into rice and to characterize the nature of extra chromosome of wild species in monosomic alien addition lines (MAALs) using molecular markers.

The material comprised parents (*O. sativa* cultivar IR56 and an elite breeding line IR31917-45-3-2, *O. brachyantha* accession 101232, and *O. granulata* accession 100879), F₁, BC₁, and advanced backcross progenies. We analyzed 30 derivatives (12 BC₃F₃, 11BC₃F₅, 7 MAALs) of *O. sativa*/*O. brachyantha* and 40 derivatives (32 BC₂F₃, 5 BC₃F₁, 3 BC₄F₁) of *O. sativa*/*O. granulata*. RFLP analysis was carried out using mapped markers on chromosomes 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, and 12 (Causse et al 1994). Forty-seven markers comprising 27 cDNA and 20 genomic probes were used with seven restriction enzymes (*Eco*RI, *Eco*RV, *Dra*I, *Hind*III, *Bam*HI, *Xba*I, *Sca*I). The hybridizations and washings were carried out at 60 °C under high salt conditions.

All of the marker-enzyme combinations, except a few, were polymorphic (see table). The hybridization signal intensities for the marker-specific target DNA sequences, done under conditions permissible to detect 70-75% DNA homology (washing stringency of 2X SSC at 60 °C), were moderate to low for most of the markers in both the wild parents, especially *O. granulata* (see table). The divergence was pronounced for chromosomes 9 and 12

specific-marker sequences in both wild species.

Five MAALs of *O. brachyantha*, which were identified based on phenotypic and cytological observations, were confirmed at the molecular level. In most of the MAALs, the alien chromosome was modified.

Despite the high divergence of alien genomes from cultivated rice, introgressions were detected for a few of the markers in the derivatives from both of the crosses (Fig. 1a). The analysis of *O. granulata* derivatives revealed two new MAALs for chromosomes 9 and 11 (Fig. 1b). In general, the frequency of introgression was low. Several markers detected nonparental bands in wide-cross derivatives (Fig. 1b). About half of these involved modification(s) of *Eco*RI-specific alleles. Further analysis is under way to determine why such bands occurred.

The results showed that the genomes of *O. brachyantha* and *O. granulata* are highly diverged from that of cultivated rice, with *O. granulata* being more diverse. Despite high divergence, chromatin material can get introgressed into cultivated rice from distantly related genomes of *Oryza*. The occurrence of nonparental bands in wide crosses is probably due to genome repatterning resulting from the interaction between unrelated genomes.

Cited reference

Causse MA, Fulton TM, Cho YG, Ahn SN, Chunwongse J, Wu K, Xiao J, Yu Z, Ronald PC, Harrington SE, Second G. McCouch SR, Tanksley SD. 1994. Saturated molecular map of the rice genome based on an interspecific backcross population. *Genetics* 138:1251-1274. ■

Polymorphism and hybridization signal intensities for marker-specific target DNA sequences in the wild parents relative to those of *O. sativa*.

Chromosome	Markers tested (no.)	Polymorphic markers (%)	Monomorphic marker-enzyme combinations		Markers with null phenotype		Hybridization signal ^a (%)	
			<i>O. granulata</i>	<i>O. brachyantha</i>	<i>O. granulata</i>	<i>O. brachyantha</i>	<i>O. granulata</i>	<i>O. brachyantha</i>
6	9	100 ^{bc}	1/63	2/63	2	2	20:50	50:100
7	9	100	2/63	2/63	1 ^d	1 ^d	30:50	35:100
9	8	100	0/56	0/56	1 ^d	0	10:20	20:40
10	6	100	1/42	1/42	1	1	30:50	35:100
11	8	100	1/56	1/56	1	1	20:50	40:100
12	7	100	0/49	0/49	1 ^d	0	10:20	20:30
Total	47	100	5/329	6/329	8	5		

^a Under relaxed conditions of hybridizations and washings permissible to detect 70.75% DNA homology relative to *O. sativa*. ^b For at least five restriction enzymes. ^c Markers with null phenotype are considered polymorphic. ^d No discrete bands: signal highly dispersed: *O. sativa* alleles multicopy.

Dra1 - RFLP patterns of introgression lines (*O. sativa*/*O. granulata*). Lanes. λ - molecular weight marker; 1-10 and 14-23 - different derived lines; 11 - *O. sativa* IR31917-45-3-2; 12- *O. granulata* (acc. 100879); 13-F₁ hybrid. a) Probe RZ884, chromosome 6. See *O. granulata*-specific allele in lanes 2 and 3 (marked with arrow). b) Probe R2797, chromosome 11. Nonparental band in lane 1 and *O. granulata* alleles in derived-MAALs for chromosome 11 (lanes 6 and 7).

Acrotrisomics in rice

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Researchers have extensively used primary trisomics in genetic mapping of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). However, no information

existed previously on the occurrence of acrotrisomics in rice.

We isolated six acrotrisomic plants from selfed progenies of primary trisomics and from the F₁ obtained from pollination of primary trisomics with irradiated pollen. An extra chromosome was identified in these acrotrisomics. One of the acrotrisomics was used in chromosome mapping.

Triplo 4, with liguleless gene (*lg lg lg*), and Triplo 7 were used for crossing as female plants. Among the F₁ plants,

acrotrisomic-like plants were selected based on the phenomenon of pseudo-dominance (Triplo 4) and abnormal morphological characters (Triplo 7). In the progenies of primary trisomics (Triplo 4, 5, 7, and 11), acrotrisomic-like plants showed abnormal morphological characters spontaneously.

Among the selected plants, six acrotrisomics were identified by mitotic chromosome analysis (Acro4S^{4L}-a, Acro4S^{4L}-b, Acro5, Acro 11) and/or restriction fragment